

Trends of Urbanization in India: Issues and Challenges

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Abstract

The highly populated urban residential area consisting mostly of closely packed, decrepit housing units in a situation of deteriorated or incomplete infrastructure, inhabited primarily by impoverished persons treated as a slum. It is a part of the city/town where the housing is a low quality and living conditions are poor. While slums differ in size and other characteristics, mostly lack reliable sanitation services, supply of clean water, reliable electricity, and other basic services. Slum residences vary from shanty houses to professionally built dwellings, which, because of poor-quality construction or provision of basic maintenance have deteriorated. The sprouting of slums in the urban areas is the direct outcome of greater economic opportunities available in the cities and towns. The demonstration effect of improved standard of living prevailing in the urban area has also attracted not only the population from smaller settlements, but also the rural migrants to almost all the major urban centers resulting in the emergence of slums even in the heart of the cities/towns. These slums occurred due to various factors such as shortage of developed land being beyond the reach of urban poor, large influx of population, rural migration to cities in search of jobs and inadequate provision of basic amenities and infrastructural facilities in the urban areas. In general, slums are the products of failed policies, bad governance, corruption, inappropriate regulation, dysfunctional land markets, unresponsive financial systems and a fundamental lack of political will.

Key Words: Infrastructure, Sanitation, Rural Migrants, corruption and Governance.

Introduction

Urbanization and economic growth are closely inter linked. The cities/towns are engines of economic growth. They are reservoirs of skill and capital and the source of divorce formal and informal sector employment opportunities. The urban areas in India are accommodating less than one-third of the country's population and its contribution to GDP is

far larger. Its share increased from 38 percent in 1970-71 to 52 percent in 1999-00. The urban share of GDP was about 63 percent in 2009-10. As India moves ahead towards a double digit growth, an obvious and key policy issue that has emerged is how to rejuvenate and strengthen urban India, which will significantly contribute and sustain the growth momentum.

Urban poor, including slum dwellers have to play a key role in the development of cities/towns. Their number is so large that even a small increase in their productivity through intervention by governments will mean that the contribution of GDP will be huge. Hence, the urban poverty need to be tackled both on equity and efficiency grounds. A striking feature of the trends in urbanization in India is the shift in the focus of poverty to cities and towns. According to the planning commission, as on 2010, the urban poor is 76 million. A large part of the urban population occurred in slums due to the natural growth factor and inability of migrants in cities/towns other than slums. As per 2011 census, the slum households in India are about 13.70 million.

The slums are characterized by acute overcrowding, insanitary, unhealthy and dehumanizing living conditions. They are subject to insecure land tenure, lack of access to basic minimum services such as safe drinking water, sanitation, storm drainage, solid waste management, internal and approach roads, street lighting, education and health care and poor quality of shelter. A significant number of slum dwellers are facing social burdens and health problems worse than their non-slum and rural counterparts.

Urbanization is one the rise as the global urban population exceeded the global rural population in recent years. The number of urban dwellers increased from 220 million in 1900 to 732 million in 1950 and is estimated to have reached 3.9 billion in 2015. The number of urban cities/towns in India are 7,935 as per census 2011. This comprised 4,011 statutory towns and 3,894 census towns compared to the figures of 3,799 and 1,362 respectively. The 7,935 urban settlements in 2011 contained a population of about 377 million representing 31 percent of the total population. The number of dwellers accounted for about 10 percent of the urban population of the world and about 12 percent of that of Asia.

The table 3.1 reveals the trends in total, rural and urban population along with the level of urbanization during 1901 to 2011 in India. The total population of India over a period of time increased from 238.40 million in 1901 to 1210.50 million by 2011. The number of urban agglomerations /towns were 1917 in India in 1901 and increased to 3059 by 1951.

From 1951 to 2011, the number of cities/towns again increased to 7933. The urban population increased from 25.80 million i.e., 10.80% of total population to 377.10 million with 31.20% of total population of the country.

Review of Literature

Lalit Batra, 'A Review of Urbanization and Urban Policy in Post-Independent India', (2009) in this paper, he tries to give insight into the existence of urban policy starting from the British rule to the post independent period (here the shift in urban policy in every Five-Year Plan period) and more importantly, the current neo liberal reforms undergoing in the field of urban affairs. Ministry of Urban Development, Government of India, (2011) 'Report on Indian Urban Infrastructure and Services'. According to this report, the urbanization in India is inevitable thus, the need for solving the various problems associated with it requires a combination of actions, starting with increased investment; strengthening the framework for governance, and most importantly capacity building for the people and the institutions engage in urban affairs

Concept of Urbanization

Urbanization: A Concept In the year 1950, only about 30% of the world population lived in urban areas, which were increased to above 50% in 2012. It was estimated that by the year 2030 more than 70% of world people will be lived in urban areas. The term 'urbanization' means the increasing share of a nation's population living in urban areas [and thus a declining share living in rural areas]. A nation's urban population can grow from natural increase [births minus deaths], net rural to urban migration and reclassification [as what was previously a rural settlement becomes classified as urban or as an urban settlement's boundaries are expanded, bringing into its population people who were previously classified as rural](Satterthwaite; Gordon, and Tacoli., 2010). According to the Census definition of India, an urban area consists of (Census of India, 2011): 1) All Statutory Towns: All places with a Municipality, Corporation, Cantonment Board or Notified Town Area Committee, etc. so declared by State law; and 2) Census Towns: which places and satisfy following criteria:- • a minimum population of 5000 ; • at least 75% of male working population engaged in non agricultural pursuits; and • a density of population of at least 400 persons per sq km. Furthermore, Population Census in India classifies urban settlement into six size classes as per the limits indicated below (Kundu, 2001):

Population Size	Category
100,000 and more	Class I
50,000 to 100,000	Class II
20,000 to 50,000	Class III
10,000 to 20,000	Class IV
5,000 to 10,000	Class V
Less than 5,000	Class V

Objective of the study

- To know the Urban Population Trend in India
- To know the Problems of Urbanization and Slum Dwellers
- To study the reasons for the Migration and Urbanization

Data Collection and Analysis

This study is based on Secondary data offers the foundation of this search. Using secondary information, historical analysis, Census examines past occurrences and trends in order to spot trends and patterns that can guide contemporary study. Mainly data analysed through percentages and annual growth rates.

Table 3.1: Urban Population and Levels of Urbanisation in India (1901-2011)

Year	Total Population (in Millions)	No. of UAs/Towns	Urban Population (in Millions)	% of Urban Population	Annual Exponential Growth Rate
1901	238.40	1917	25.80	10.80	---
1911	252.10	1909	25.90	10.30	0.03
1921	251.30	2047	28.10	11.20	0.79
1931	278.90	2219	33.40	12.00	1.75
1941	318.60	2424	44.10	13.90	2.77
1951	361.10	3059	62.40	17.30	3.47
1961	439.20	2699	78.90	18.00	2.34
1971	548.20	3126	109.10	19.90	3.21
1981	683.30	3949	159.50	23.30	3.83
1991	846.30	4615	217.60	25.70	3.09
2001	1028.60	5161	286.10	27.80	2.73
2011	1210.50	7933	377.10	31.20	2.76

Source: Census of India, 2011

The level of degree of urbanization or the percentage to total population stood at 10.30 percent in 1911. It shows that 17.30 percent of the population lived in cities and towns

of India by 1051. The percentage of urban population significantly increased to 23.30 percent in 1981, 25.70 percent in 1991 and reached to 27.80 percent in 2001. Finally it increased to 31.16 percent as per 2011 census. The diagram 3.1 illustrates the levels of urbanization in India.

Diag. 3.1: Urban Population and Levels of Urbanisation in India (1901-2011)

Trends in Global Urban Population and Growth of Slums

According to the 2011, Revision of the World Urbanization Prospects, UN, Asian and African regions together accounts for 86 percent of increase in the world’s urban population. Africa’s urban population will be increased from 414 million to over 1.2 billion by 2050 while that of Asia will rise from 1.9 billion to 3.3 billion. This will pose a new challenges of providing urban jobs, housing, energy and infrastructure to mitigate urban poverty, expansion of slums and a deterioration of the urban environment. The following table 3.2 reveals the trends in urbanization in some of the countries of the world as on 2011.

Table 3.2: Trends (in Percentage) in the Urbanization of the selected Countries in the World- 2011

S. No.	Country/Year	2008	2009	2010	2011
1.	Afghanistan	23	23	23	24
2.	Bangladesh	27	27	28	28
3.	Bhutan	33	34	35	36
4.	China	47	48	49	51
5.	Thailand	33	33	34	34
6.	Egypt	43	43	43	44
7.	Angola	57	57	58	59
8.	Algeria	70	71	72	73
9.	Bahrain (UK)	89	89	89	89

10.	Uganda	14	15	15	16
11.	America (US)	82	82	82	82
12.	Canada	80	80	81	81
13.	Argentina	92	92	92	92
14.	Chill	88	89	89	89
15.	Brazil	84	84	84	85
16.	Germany	74	74	74	74
17.	Britain	79	79	80	80
18.	Turkey	69	70	70	71
19.	Australia	89	89	89	89

Source: 2011 Revision of World Urbanization Projects, United Nations.

It reveals that most of the country’s urban population has been increased by one percent or more, but the growth of urbanization is constant for the four years i.e. from 2008 to 2011 in Bahrain (UK), America (US), Cuba, Argentina, Germany and Australia. The percentage of urbanization in these six countries varied between 72 and 92 percent. In china, urban population increased by 4 percent followed by Bhutan with 3 percent. In Angola, Uganda, and Turkey its urban growth is 2 percent during 2008 to 2011. The trends in the urbanization of the selected countries is diagrammatically shown in diagram 3.2.

Diag. 3.2: Trends (in Percentage) in the Urbanization of the selected Countries in the World- 2011

Literacy Levels among Slum Dwellers in India

The literacy rate of total population is high (98.11%) in Mizoram followed by Kerala and low in Chandigarh (66.38%). The literacy rate among slum population is high ((88.78%) in Mizoram followed by Meghalaya (88.10%) and low in Chandigarh (52.10%). The literacy level of slum dwellers in Andhra Pradesh is 68.90 percent against 75.32 percent among urban households. The literacy level of slum dwellers in Chandigarh is 52.20 percent against 66.38

percent of literacy among urban households. The literacy rate among slum dwellers of Mizoram is 88.78 percent followed by Meghalaya with 88.10 percent. Overall, the literacy rate of slum population of India fluctuates between 52.20 percent and 88.78 percent against a fluctuation of 66.38 percent and 98.11 percent among urban population. The average literacy rate of slum dwellers in India is 71.65 percent against 77.72 percent of urban literacy rate of India as shown table 3.3.

Migration in India

The twenty first century is witnessing sustained population growth together with urbanization and industrialization. Cities have always been the epicenter of economic growth. The economic vibrancy of these large urban centres offers diverse employment opportunities and means of livelihood. Migration, urbanization and mushrooming growth of slums are direct manifestations of the process of economic development, particularly in the contemporary phase of globalization.

Table 3.3: State Wise Literacy Levels of Slum Dwellers in India (2011 Census)

S.No.	State/UT	Literacy level of Total Population	Literacy Level of Slum Dwellers
1.	A&N Islands	82.80	76.35
2.	Andhra Pradesh	75.32	68.90
3.	Arunachal Pradesh	69.39	62.17
4.	Assam	81.57	74.55
5.	Bihar	68.15	56.70
6.	Chandigarh	66.38	52.20
7.	Chhattisgarh	80.36	74.20
8.	Delhi	75.16	65.60
9.	Goa	82.44	60.85
10.	Gujarat	70.49	64.25
11.	Haryana	75.87	71.50
12.	Himachal Pradesh	87.74	82.25
13.	Jammu& Kashmir	68.02	66.90
14.	Jharkhand	75.51	71.65
15.	Karnataka	75.63	67.25
16.	Kerala	93.11	84.75
17.	Madhya Pradesh	77.25	73.25
18.	Maharashtra	84.55	79.35
19.	Meghalaya	89.02	88.10
20.	Mizoram	98.11	88.78
21.	Nagaland	88.85	80.32
22.	Odisha	78.95	70.00
23.	Puducherry	81.39	74.25

24.	Punjab	74.18	71.20
25.	Rajasthan	69.79	63.50
26.	Tamil Nadu	82.06	76.70
27.	Tripura	90.71	86.50
28.	Uttar Pradesh	68.98	62.50
29.	Uttarakhand	76.88	66.70
30.	West Bengal	81.38	74.05
	India	77.72	71.65

Source: Census of India 2011.

Displacement of labour force from the rural economy and their absorption in urban sectors have created serious stress in cities and towns. The capacity of the cities and towns to assimilate the migrants by providing employment, access to land, basic amenities etc., are limited. The problem has acquired severity as migrants have shown high selectivity in choosing their destinations leading to growth of slums. In India, migration played a predominant role in accelerated urban growth which concomitantly attracts the rural migrants to the urban areas for economic reasons regardless of the fact that physical infrastructure in terms of housing, drinking water supply, drainage, sanitation etc., are not adequate in the cities/towns. The problem of slum is now a common feature of almost all major Indian cities. The quality of life thus, suffers due to continuous influx of migrants and consequently widens the gap between demand and supply of essential services and other infrastructure in urban areas.

Migration is a major contribution in the slum population. An important feature of urbanization in Indian during the period 1981-2001 was the relatively small contribution of migration to the increase in urban population of India. The net migration from rural to urban contributes about 21.70 percent increase in 1990s. In 1961 it was 13.80 percent and decreased to 6.20 percent in 2001. The pressure of rural-urban migration will increase due to an increasing role of industry and services sector in growth and due to more labour absorbing growth resulting from increasing integration with the world economy.

The table 3.4 shows the internal migrants in various categories during 1961 to 2001. It shows that inter-censal migration declined from 15 percent in 1961 to 9.5 percent in 2001 with a total inter-censal migrants of 98.30 million during 1961-2001. The percentage of inter-censal- interstate migrants also declined from 2 percent in 1961 to 1.30 percent in 1991 and increased to 1.60 percent in 2001 with a total inter-censal and inter-state migrants of 16.80 million. The life time migrants' percentage has been fluctuated between 26.50 percent in

1991 and 30.60 percent in 1961 with a total lifetime migrants of 301.10 million. The lifetime interstate migrants have been increased from 3.30 percent to 4.20 percent.

Regarding to the percent of rural inter-censal migrants, it has significantly declined from 8.40 percent to 4 percent during 1961-2001. Life time rural migrants share declined from 13.90 percent in 1961 to 9.40 percent in 1991. The percent of inter-censal urban migration declined from 7.90 percent to 4.10 percent and lifetime urban migrants share declined to 37.70 percent to 26 percent during 1961 to 1991 and increased to 31.20 percent in 2001.

Table 3.4: Internal Migrants in Various Categories in India during 1961-2011

Category	Percentage to Total population					Total Migrants in Millions
	1961	1971	1981	1991	2001	2011
Total Migrants						
Inter-censal	15.00	12.40	12.20	9.70	9.50	98.30
Inter-censal Interstate	2.00	1.60	1.60	1.30	1.60	16.80
Lifetime	30.60	28.70	29.40	26.50	29.20	301.10
Lifetime Interstate	3.30	3.40	3.60	3.30	4.20	42.30
Total Migrants						
Inter-censal	8.40	7.10	6.30	4.20	4.00	15.20
Inter-censal Interstate	0.90	0.80	0.70	0.50	0.60	2.30
Lifetime	13.90	12.90	11.50	9.40	10.50	40.20
Lifetime Interstate	1.40	1.30	1.20	0.90	1.10	4.40
Total Migrants						
Inter-censal	23.80	18.50	16.90	11.70	11.70	17.70
Inter-censal Interstate	7.90	5.60	4.40	3.30	4.10	6.20
Lifetime	37.50	33.60	32.40	26.00	31.20	47.00
Lifetime Interstate	12.30	11.20	10.00	8.00	10.20	15.30

Source: Census India, 2011,

Note: Lifetime migrants are by their place of birth while inter-censal migrants are by their place of last residence for reasons of temporal comparability.

Trends in Global Slum Population

Around one-third of the urban population in developing countries with one billion population are living in slums in the world. The Un-HABITAT estimated that the world’s slum population may be 889 million by 2010. It reveals that between 2000- 2010, the number of slum dwellers increased by six million every year in the world. It shows that 70 percent of Africa’s urban population lives in the slums. The majority of the slum dwellers in African cities are between the age of 15 and 24 years.

The slums are often economically vibrant and today about 85 percent of all new employment opportunities around the world occur in the informal economy. Although there are more men than women in the workforce, women make up 60 to 80 percent of the informal workforce in developing countries as per International Labour Organization. It may also be observed that more than 50 percent of the urban population in South Asia and 40 percent in Sub-Saharan Africa lack access to sanitation services. It reveals that there is one toilet for every 500 population in the slums of Nairobi, Kenya.

Slum Population in India

A heavily populated urban area characterized by substandard housing and squalor grows up in a slum near downtown, lived in the slums by river belt or drain belt or in a low level water flowing area with congested roads and drains. The 21st century has witnessed a rapid growth of urban population coupled with incommensurate development of social facilities which has resulted in the creation of slums associated with problems of an alarming magnitude. Owing to lack of employment and suitable jobs in the countryside, people from rural areas migrate to the towns/cities. In cities, they obtain jobs but their income hardly allows them to have good accommodation or neighborhood.

Hence, they occupy vacant land or try to adjust themselves in the existing slums. This results in a growth of slums and slum dwellers. For the purpose of enumerating slums in India in 2001 census, slum blocks were identified in 1743 cities/towns having more than 20,000 population, spread across 26 states and Union Territories all over India. However, in 2011 census, slum blocks have been delineated in all statutory towns irrespective of population size. For the purpose of census, slums have been categorized as Notified slums, Recognized slums and Identified slums.

As per 2011 census, there are 7933 towns in India with 4041 statutory towns and 2543 slum reporting towns. The total number of urban households in India are 788.70 lakhs with 137.50 lakh slum households and 651.20 non-slum households. The percentage of slum households in the total urban households in the country are 17.40 percent against 82.60 percent of non-slum households.

The percentage of urban population to total population is high in Delhi with 97.50 percent followed by 97.25 percent in Chandigarh (Table 3.5). In the States of India, it varied between 10.03 percent in Himachal Pradesh to 52.11 percent in Mizoram. The percentage of

slum dwellers are more 12.04% in combined Andhra Pradesh and low (1.12) percent in Arunachal Pradesh.

Its inhabitants are mostly uneducated in many slum areas in India in general and in Andhra Pradesh in particular. The table 3.5 presents the state wise male and female slum population of India. It reveals that the highest urban populated city is Delhi with 97.50 percent followed by Chandigarh with 97.25 percent. Among the Indian states, the percentage of urban population varied between 52.10 percent in Mizoram and 10.03 percent in Himachal Pradesh. The percentage of urban population of Andhra Pradesh is 34.18 percent as per 2011 census. The percentage of slum population is more in Andhra Pradesh with 12.04 percent followed by Maharashtra with 10.54 percent.

Table 3.5: State Wise Male and Female Slum Dwellers in India (2011 Census)

State/UT	Total Population	% of Urban Population	% of Slum Population	% of Male Slum Population	% of Female Slum Population
A&N Islands	380581	37.70	3.72	52.12	47.88
Andhra Pradesh	84580777	34.18	12.04	50.10	49.90
Arunachal Pradesh	1383727	22.94	1.12	51.59	48.41
Assam	31205576	14.10	0.63	51.42	48.58
Bihar	104099452	11.29	1.19	56.11	43.89
Chandigarh	1055450	97.25	9.01	56.07	49.10
Chhattisgarh	25545198	23.24	7.43	50.90	45.43
Delhi	16787941	97.50	10.63	54.57	47.32
Goa	1458545	62.17	1.80	52.68	45.68
Gujarat	60439692	42.60	2.78	54.32	46.58
Haryana	25351462	34.88	6.56	53.42	46.90
Himachal Pradesh	6864602	10.03	0.89	53.10	48.28
Jammu& Kashmir	12267032	26.11	5.28	51.72	48.28
Jharkhand	32988134	24.05	1.13	51.72	48.28
Karnataka	61095297	38.67	5.39	50.15	49.85
Kerala	33406061	47.70	0.60	48.22	51.78
Madhya Pradesh	72626809	27.63	7.83	51.99	48.01
Maharashtra	112374333	45.22	10.54	53.41	46.59
Meghalaya	2966889	20.07	1.94	51.68	48.32
Mizoram	1097206	52.11	7.16	49.47	50.53
Nagaland	1978502	28.86	4.16	51.81	48.19
Odisha	41974218	16.69	3.72	51.33	48.67
Puducherry	1247953	68.33	11.58	48.76	51.24
Punjab	27743338	37.48	5.26	53.16	46.84
Rajasthan	68548437	24.87	3.02	52.18	47.82
Tamil Nadu	72147030	48.40	8.04	49.79	50.21

Tripura	3673917	26.17	3.80	50.18	49.82
Uttar Pradesh	199812341	22.27	3.12	52.86	47.14
Uttarakhand	10086292	30.23	4.84	52.82	47.18
West Bengal	91276115	31.87	7.03	51.75	48.25
India	1210854977	31.16	5.41	51.86	48.14

Source: Census of India 2011 data

The slum population is low in Kerala with only 0.60 percent. The percentage of male slum population in the Indian states varied from 56.11 percent in Bihar to 48.22 percent in Kerala. In regarding to Union Territories it varied between 56.07 percent in Chandigarh and 48.76 percent in Puducherry. The percentage of female slum population is high in Kerala with 51.78 percent and low (43.89%) in Bihar. The percentage of female slum population of India is 48.14n percent as per 2011 census.

Top and Bottom Five Slum Households in India

As a percentage of total urban households in India, Andhra Pradesh has the highest proportion of slum dweller households with 35.70 percent followed by Chhattisgarh with 31.90 percent, Madhya Pradesh with 28.30 percent and West Bengal with 21.90 percent. Kerala has the lowest proportion of slum households to urban households with 1.5 percent followed by Assam 4.80 percent, Jharkhand with 5.30 percent, Gujarat with 6.70 percent and Chandigarh with 9.70 percent as shown in table 3.6 and diagram 3.3 and 3.4.

Table 3.6: Top and Bottom Five Slum Households States in India (2011)

Top Five Slum Households States	% of Slum Households to Urban Households	Bottom Five Slum Households States	% of Slum Households to Urban Households
Andhra Pradesh	35.70	Chandigarh	9.70
Chhattisgarh	31.90	Gujarat	6.70
Madhya Pradesh	28.30	Jharkhand	5.30
Odisha	23.10	Assam	4.80
West Bengal	21.90	Kerala	1.50

Source: Census of India 2011

Diag 3.3: Top Five Slum Households States in India

Diag 3.4: Bottom Five Slum Households States in India

Reasons for Increased Slum Population in India

The general reasons for the increase of slum dwellers are due to industrialisation in urban areas, migration from rural to urban, lack of employment opportunities in the rural areas of India where agriculture is the basic industry to provide seasonal employment that too which depends on rainfall and other natural conditions. The low wages and inadequate infrastructural facilities for living of the migrant people in urban India is also one of the cause.

Industrialization has been increased in the country and large as well as medium-sized industries have been established in several parts of the country. The industrial concerns have attracted the rural masses for employment. The uneconomic subdivision of holdings from generation to generation and unprofitable agriculture which suffering from periodic famines,

floods, pestilences and other calamities have aggravated the problem of increase of slum population.

Most of towns/cities are congested and overcrowded with the lack of civil amenities when people thrown into the cities to work in industries in construction work, in transport and trading Corporations and they fail to find housing accommodation. If there are thousands of industrial workers without residential facilities they try to make some temporary arrangements near the place of their work. Whenever they find vacant Government land, large number of unhygienic huts spring up near the factories or commercial concerns. These naturally turn into slums because the area is small, proper roads are not available, facilities like electricity, water and toilet room facilities do not exist as the large number of urban workers are unskilled labourers and earning low wages. Many of them are employed on temporary basis. They cannot afford to have cement-mortar houses with proper facilities and they are forced to live in slums.

Classification of Slums

As per 2011 census of India, the total number of enumeration blocks are 1,08,227 and out of them 37,072 (34.30%) are notified slums, 30,846 (28.50%) are recognized slums and 40,309 (37.20%) are identified slums in the country. From all these slums, 137.50 lakh of urban households with 17.40 percent are living in the slums and out of 137.50 lakh total slum households, 49.65 lakh with 36.10 percent of the households are living in the notified slums, 37.96 lakh (27.60%) of the households are living in recognized slums and 49.88 lakh with 36.30 percent of the households are living in identified slums as shown table 3.7 and diagram 3.5.

Table 3.7: Number of Different Type of Slums and Households in India (2011)

Category of Slum	Number of Slums	Percentage	Households (in Lakhs)	Percentage
Notified Slums	37,072	34.30	49.65	36.10
Recognized Slums	30,846	28.50	37.96	27.60
Identified Slums	40,309	37.20	49.88	36.30
Total Slums	1,08,227	100.00	137.49	100.00

Source: Census of India, 2011

Diag. 3.5: Number of Different Type of Slums and Households in India (2011)

Table 3.11: Slum Houses Constructed by Using Different Materials for Roofs (in Lakhs)

Area	Total Houses	Material Used for Roofs of Slum Houses					
		Grass, Thatch, Bamboo, Mud, Plastic and Polythene	Hand Made Tiles	Machine Made Tiles	Burnt Bricks, Stone, Slate, Concrete	GI Material, Asbestos Sheets	Other Material
Urban	983.20	48.70 (5.00)	54.50 (6.00)	63.30 (6.00)	652.50 (66.00)	159.60 (16.00)	4.40 (0.40)
Slum	159.90	12.20 (8.00)	13.10 (8.00)	10.90 (7.00)	81.30 (51.00)	41.60 (26.00)	0.90 (1.00)

Source: Census of India 2011

The slum houses with roof made of tiles are 24 lakhs with 15 percent total slum houses including 13.10 lakh handmade tiles and 10.90 lakh machine made tiles. Houses with roof made of burnt brick, stone, slate and concrete are 81.30 lakh houses with 51 percent of total slum houses. Houses with roof made of GI metal, asbestos sheets are 41.60 lakhs with 26 percent of total slum houses and 0.90 lakh houses are with roof made of other materials based on local conditions. The table 3.11 and diagram 3.7 shows the type of materials used for roofs of slum dwellings in India.

Diag. 3.6: Slum Houses Constructed by Using Different Materials for Roofs

Material of Walls of Dwellings of Slum Households in India

The table 3.12 reveals that out of 137.50 lakh slum dweller households in India, 65 percent are occupied the houses with walls made of burnt bricks and concrete where as 14 percent of slum households of India occupied the houses with walls made of stone.

Table 3.12: Type of Material Used for the Walls of Slum Houses in India (2011)

Area	No. of Households (in Lakhs)	Type of Material used for Walls of Slum Houses (in Lakhs)						
		Grass, Thatch, Bamboo, Plastic, Polythene	Mud, Unburnt Bricks	Wood, GI Metal, Asbestos Sheets	Stone		Burnt Brick. Concrete Other Materials	
					Not Packed with Mortar	Packed with Mortar		
Urban	788.70	23.9 (3.00)	73.30 (9.00)	10.80 (1.00)	21.70 (3.00)	96.80 (12.00)	557.80 (71.00)	4.40 (1.00)
Slum	137.50	5.80 (4.00)	18.80 (14.00)	3.30 (2.00)	4.20 (3.00)	15.40 (11.00)	89.30 (65.00)	0.70 (1.00)

Source: Census of India 2011

Out of 14 percent households, 3 percent of slum households occupied the houses with walls made of stone not packed with mortar and 11 percent houses with walls made of stone packed with mortar. Another 14 percent of slum households occupied the houses with wall made of unburnt bricks, 4 percent occupied the houses with wall made of grass, thatch, bamboo, plastic and polythene etc., About 2 percent of slum dwellers occupied the houses with wall made of wood, GI metals, asbestos sheets and one percent occupied the houses with walls made of other materials.

Condition of Houses Occupied by Slum Dwellers

Among 137.50 lakh slum dweller households in India, 80.30 lakh households comprising 58 percent of slum households are living in good conditioned houses, 51.60 lakhs slum dwellers comprising 38 percent of slum dwellers are living in livable houses and 4 percent of slum dwellers are living in dilapidated stage houses with insecurity. On the other side, 68 percent of urban households in India are living in good condition houses, 29 percent are living in livable houses and 3 percent are living in dilapidated stage houses as shown in table 3.14 below. It may also noticed that 68 percent of urban houses are in good condition and 29 percent of urban houses are in livable conditions only.

Table 3.14: Condition of Houses Occupied Slum Dwellers in India (2011)

Area	Households	Condition of Houses		
		Good	Livable	Dilapidated
Urban	788.70	539.80 (68.00)	226.10 (29.00)	22.70 (3.00)
Slum	137.50	80.30 (58.00)	51.60 (38.00)	5.50 (4.00)

Source: Census of India 2011

Number of Dwelling Rooms in the Houses of Slums in India (2011)

The number of dwelling rooms available in a house indicates the status of the resident dweller and also convenient to the family members to live under one roof with many. The table 3.15 shows the number of dwelling rooms available in the houses of slum dweller households in the country with a comparison of urban dwellers with number of dwelling rooms in the houses. Out of 137.50 lakh slum dwellings in the country, 61.60 lakh representing 45 percent of slum households have two dwelling rooms in the slum houses against 31 percent of urban resident houses. It may also noticed that 45 percent of slum dwellers have one dwelling room in their houses against the urban dwellers with 32 percent having one dwelling room. Three dwelling rooms are available in 12 percent of slum houses and in 18 percent of urban houses. There are four rooms and above in 12.30 percent of slum houses and in 16 percent of urban houses. No exclusive rooms are there in 4 percent slum houses and in 3 percent of urban houses.

Table 3.15: Number of Dwellings in the Slum and Urban Houses in India-2011 (in Lakhs)

Area	No. of Households	Number of Dwellings in Slum/Urban Houses			
		No Exclusive	01 Room	02 Rooms	03 Rooms

		Room				Rooms
Urban	788.70	24.30 (3.00)	253.40 (32.00)	241.40 (31.00)	144.90 (18.00)	124.70 (16.00)
Slum	137.50	6.00 (4.00)	61.60 (45.00)	40.60 (30.00)	17.00 (12.00)	12.30 (9.00)

Source: Census of India 2011

Tenure Status of Dwellings of Slum Households

As shown in table 3.16, out of total slum families in the country, 70 percent of the families have their own house in the slums as compared to 69 percent in non-slum households in urban India. It shows that out of 788.70 lakh non slum dwellers in the urban areas, 28 percent of urban households are residing in rented houses against 26 percent of slum households residing in rented houses. Only 4 percent among slum dwellers and 3 percent among non-slum dweller households are living in other type of houses.

Table 3.16: Ownership of House of Dwellers in Slum/Urban Areas -2011

Area	No. of Households	Ownership Status of Households (in Lakhs)		
Urban	788.70	545.40 (69.00)	217.20 (28.00)	26.00 (3.00)
Slum	135.50	96.60 (70.00)	36.10 (26.00)	4.80 (4.00)

Source: Census of India 2011

Availability of Drinking Water Facility in the Slums

Access to basic amenities in a developing nation is one of the major yardsticks to measure the socio-economic development. Improved basic amenities lead to improved health, reduced child mortality, improved water quality, environment and economic growth of a Nation. Continued migration to urban areas, congregation of urban poor in slums without safe water supply, inadequate sanitation leads to poor quality of life in the slums.

As per 2011 census of India, tap, hand pumps, and other tube wells/bore wells together constituted the major source of drinking water in Indian slums. Out of 137.50 lakh slum households of India, 101.90 lakh slum dwellers (74 %) have access to tap water as a source of drinking water in the slums. While 28 lakh (20%) slum households have access to well as a source of drinking water and 3 percent of slum dwellers have access to other sources such as spring, canal, river, tank, pond, lake and others as a source of drinking water in slum areas of India.

Availability of Separate Kitchen Facility for Slum Dwellers

Table 3.17 reveals that out of 137.50 lakh slum dwellers in the country, 94 percent of slum dwellers have inside cooking facility and out of them, 65 percent slum dwellers with kitchen facility inside the house, while, 29 percent without kitchen inside the house. It may also noticed that 5.40 percent of slum dweller households cook food outside the house and 0.50 percent of slum dwellers does not have any type of kitchen facility in the houses as per census 2011 data. It may also noticed that 78 percent of urban households have a kitchen facility in their houses.

Table 3.17: Availability of Separate Kitchen Facilities in the Dwellings of Slum Households in India-2011 (in Lakhs)

Area	No. of Households	Availability of Separate Kitchen Facility				
		Cooking inside House		Cooking outside the House		No Cooking
		Has Kitchen	Does not Have Kitchen	Has Kitchen	Does not Have Kitchen	
Urban	788.70	613.60 (78.00)	142.00 (18.00)	12.90 (1.60)	16.10 (2.00)	4.00 (0.50)
Slum	137.50	89.80 (65.00)	39.60 (29.00)	2.80n (2.00)	4.60 (3.00)	0.70 (0.50)

Source: Census of India 2011

Availability of Latrine Room Facilities for Slum Households

In case of urban households, out of 788.70 lakh households in India, 81 percent of them have latrine room facility within the premises and remaining 19 percent of urban households does not avail latrine room facility in their homes. In the slum areas, only 66 percent of households have latrine room facility in the premises of their homes (Table 3.18). The remaining 34 percent (46.70 lakh) of slum dwellers have no toilet room facility in their houses. Out of this 46.70 lakh households, 44 percent of slum dwellers (20.70 lakh) are using public latrines and 56 percent (26 lakh) of them are following open defecation in the slum areas. It reveals that even though the governments are advising and take steps to avoid open defecation as a part of Swatch Bharat, the slum dwellers are not following and are using open spaces for toileting purpose in the country.

Table 3.18: Households Having Latrine Room Facility in the Slums of India -2011 (in Lakhs)

Area	No.of Households	Having Latrine	Not Having Latrine Facility within Premises
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		Facility within Premises	Source	
			Public Latrine	Open
Urban	788.70	641.60 (81.35)	47.50 (6.02)	99.60 (12.63)
Slum	137.50	90.70 (65.97)	20.80 (15.13)	26.00 (18.90)

Source: Census of India 2011

Type of Fuel Used for Cooking

It is observed from the census 2011 data that out of 137.50 lakh slum dwellers in India, 15 percent of households are using LPG as a main source of fuel for cooking, against 65 percent of households in urban India (Table 3.20). It may also noticed that 33 percent of slum dwellers are using firewood, crop residue, cow dung cake, coal, lignite and charcoal as a fuel for cooking, against 26 percent of urban households in India. Bio-gas is the major source of fuel for cooking for only 0.40 percent of slum dwellers and urban households. A negligible percentage of slum and urban households are using electricity and other sources as a fuel for cooking in both slum and urban India. It is interestingly observed that 0.50 percent of slum holds and urban households are not cooking food in their houses.

Table 3.20: Type of Fuel Used for Cooking by Slum Households -2011 (in Lakhs)

Area	No. of Households	Type of Fuel Used for Cooking						
		Fire wood, Crop Residue, Cow Dung, Lignite, Charcoal	Kerosene	LPG	Bio-Gas	Electricity	Other	No Cooking
Urban	788.70	206.50 (26.00)	59.30 (7.50)	512.80 (65.00)	3.20 (0.40)	1.20 (0.20)	1.50 (0.20)	4.00 (0.50)
Slum	137.50	45.90 (33.00)	19.20 (14.00)	70.50 (51.00)	0.60 (0.40)	0.20 (0.10)	0.40 (0.30)	0.70 (0.50)

Source: Census of India 2011

Conclusion

The demonstration effect of improved standard of living prevailing in the urban area has also attracted not only the population from smaller settlements, but also the rural migrants to almost all the major urban centers resulting in the emergence of slums even in the heart of the cities/towns. These slums occurred due to various factors such as shortage of developed land being beyond the reach of urban poor, large influx of population, rural migration to cities in search of jobs and inadequate provision of basic amenities and infrastructural facilities in the urban areas.

The slums are characterized by acute overcrowding, insanitary, unhealthy and dehumanizing living conditions. They are subject to insecure land tenure, lack of access to basic minimum services such as safe drinking water, sanitation, storm drainage, solid waste management, internal and approach roads, street lighting, education and health care and poor quality of shelter. A significant number of slum dwellers are facing social burdens and health problems worse than their non-slum and rural counterparts.

The number of urban dwellers increased from 220 million in 1900 to 732 million in 1950 and is estimated to have reached 3.9 billion in 2015. The number of urban cities/towns in India are 7,935 as per census 2011. This comprised 4,011 statutory towns and 3,894 census towns compared to the figures of 3,799 and 1,362 respectively. The 7,935 urban settlements in 2011 contained a population of about 377 million representing 31 percent of the total population.

The total population of India over a period of time increased from 238.40 million in 1901 to 1210.50 million by 2011. The number of urban agglomerations /towns were 1917 in India in 1901 and increased to 3059 by 1951. From 1951 to 2011, the number of cities/towns again increased to 7933. The urban population increased from 25.80 million i.e., 10.80% of total population to 377.10 million with 31.20% of total population of the country. The above discussions are focussed on availability of basic amenities in the Indian slums with a comparison of urban households and also on the conditions of slum dwellers and their dwellings. The next chapter focussed on the socio-economic characteristics of sample slum dwellers in Ananthapuramu Municipal Corporation of Andhra Pradesh.

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